

COMPARATIVE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE TC-250 OUT-OF-AUTOCLAVE MATERIAL MADE BY HAND LAY-UP AND AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT PROCESSES

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Keywords: *Automated Manufacturing, AFP, TC-250 Resin System, Out-of-Autoclave, Thermoset, Comparative Characterization*

1. Introduction

Composite materials have been extensively used for making the primary and secondary structures in the aircraft industry while continuously improving both the materials and the manufacturing processes. Today's aerospace industry is looking at the composites and automated manufacturing processes to reduce the cost and the processing time so as to cater their demands [1]. Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) process has been conceived over the years to overcome the limitations of traditional fabrication methods [2]. Numerous advantages of AFP process include faster lay-up, minimal supervision, fiber-steering, reduced scrap, improved part to part uniformity while incorporating greater complexity and part features.

In the complete process to make a composite structure, substantial cost reduction can be achieved by avoiding the Autoclave curing process. The Out-of-Autoclave (OOA) thermoset material addresses this need [3]. The OOA prepregs initially were only used for non-structural and secondary structures in the aircrafts. But recently, Airbus 350 XWB jetliner became the first commercial aircraft to employ the MTM 44-1 OOA prepreg material to make their wing panels [4]. OOA technology not only reduces capital expenditure but also very large structures manufacturing can be facilitated, sandwich structures will no more be a hassle and will also result in low cost tooling and reduced overheads.

The research work presented in this paper aims at investigating the properties of laminates manufactured using the OOA prepreg by AFP and Hand-layup (HLU) processes. A comparative study on the effects of pressure and no-pressure conditions during the curing cycle and the debulking achieved in both the manufacturing processes is also shown. A comparative cost model is also presented to understand the economics of each manufacturing technique and the associated processing conditions.

2. Material Selection

TC-250 OOA prepreg material was chosen to perform this study. It is a member of TenCate Advanced Composite's newly derived TC family of toughened matrices for structural advanced composite applications [5]. The prepreg material used for the Hand Lay-up was supplied in 12 inch wide unidirectional rolls and the material fed to the AFP machine was 0.25 inch wide unidirectional tapes. The thickness of both, the rolls and tapes was 0.0054 inches.

3. Details of Manufacturing Processes

3.1 Hand Lay-Up Technique

The TC-250 prepreg material was used to prepare the samples for Tensile, Compressive and Shear testing in accordance with the ASTM Standards. There were two sets of samples prepared using HLU process, the first set was cured in the Autoclave and the second set was cured in a Convection Oven as per the conditions outlined in the Tencates' Advanced materials TC-250 Resin System Technical Data sheet [5].

3.2 Automated Fiber Placement Process

Automated fiber placement process was used to characterize the TC-250 material. The optimum process parameters namely, speed of the lay-up, temperature and the pressure were determined after a number of trial runs. The optimized process parameters were Torch Temperature 200 °C, the prepreg lay-up rate 50 mm sec⁻¹ and pressure applied being 130 N. The two set of samples made by the AFP technique were cured in Autoclave with Pressure and No-Pressure conditions.

Figure-1 shows the cross section of vacuum bag assembly for the curing of the laid prepregs. A cowl plate was used on the top of the laminate to ensure proper uniform thickness. A thermocouple was placed directly on the sample to measure the temperature of the sample directly.

Fig.1 Cross Section of the Vacuum-bag Assembly

3.3 Autoclave and Out-of-Autoclave Curing cycle

As to ensure the curing cycle truly reflects the temperature of the composite laminate and not the oven temperature, a series of dry-runs were done and the optimum rate ($^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$) was determined using the dual loop temperature controller. Figure-2 shows the path followed by the laminate while undergoing curing process.

The only difference between the Autoclave and OOA processing was the application of pressure. In autoclave a constant pressure of about 420 - 425 kPa was applied during the curing cycle. Both the sets of laminates were post cured at 178°C for 2 hours after the primary curing cycle.

Fig.2 Curing cycle

4. Quality Control

Quality Control is a very important parameter in the characterization process [6]. Proper handling of the prepreg material, clean room requirements and clean molds are all necessary to produce uniform and quality laminates. Following parameters were used to ensure the Quality assurance process.

4.1 Degree of Cure

To check the degree of cure, the samples made by different methods were tested using the Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) machine. Heat-Cool-Heat cycle was employed for determination of degree of cure in the DSC. Minimal amount of heat absorbed by the sample testified proper curing.

4.2 Optical Microscopy

Optical microscopy was performed on the samples made by various manufacturing methods to determine the quality of the laminate by determination of voids and resin-rich areas [7].

Fig.3 HLU Sample cured without Pressure

Fig.4 HLU Sample cured with Pressure

Microscopic Images were taken to show the area in between consecutive layers in the laminates made by various techniques. Figure 3 and 4 show microscopic images of the Hand Lay-up samples. Figure-3 shows the one cured without pressure and the figure-4 shows the one cured with pressure.

It is evident from these microscopic images that the samples made by Hand lay-up and cured in Autoclave with pressure show better consolidation compared to the sample cured without pressure. The average gap between the consecutive layers in the samples cured with pressure was 6.8 mm while for the sample cured without pressure was 7.2 mm. The pressure applied in the Autoclave along with high temperatures accounts for better uniform distribution of resin and also proper consolidation of the laminate [8].

The microscopic images shown in Figure 5 and 6 are of the samples made by AFP cure without pressure and with pressure respectively.

Fig.5 AFP Sample cured without Pressure

Fig.6 AFP Sample cured with Pressure

Similar to what was observed in the HLU samples; the AFP samples cured in Autoclave with pressure had relatively better consolidation. The average gap between consecutive layers in the sample cured under pressure was 6.2 mm compared to 6.5 mm for the samples cured without pressure.

Fig.7 Resin Rich Areas

Figure-7 shows a typical resin rich area in a HLU sample. However, no major resin rich areas were observed in any of the samples, but, comparatively the AFP samples had insignificant resin rich areas compared to HLU samples. Curing with pressure resulted in comparatively less resin rich areas than curing without pressure.

From the microscopy it is clear that the Autoclave Pressure plays an important role in debulking and compaction of the prepregs. Second important observation was the pressure applied by the AFP head also helps in minimizing voids and resin rich areas. No major resin rich areas and voids were observed in the OOA cured sample [9].

5. Mechanical Testing

Mechanical tests to determine the tensile, compressive and in-plane shear properties were performed on coupons made by various manufacturing techniques and curing cycles. These tests are important to understand the behaviors of real complex structures under multi axial loads [10]. Table-1 shows the dimensions and stacking sequence of laminates manufactured using four different processes HLU+AC, HLU+OOA, AFP+AC, and AFP+OOA. The term ‘HLU+AC’ denotes a sample made by HLU and cured with pressures in Autoclave and the term ‘HLU+OOA’ denotes a sample made by HLU and cured without the application of pressure.

Table.1 Measured Property, Laminate Dimensions and Stacking sequence

Measured Property	Laminate Length / Width (mm)	Stacking Sequence
Tensile Modulus and Strength (0°)	304.8/304.8	[0] ₈
Tensile Modulus and Strength (90°)	228.6/304.8	[90] ₁₆
In-Plane Shear Modulus and Strength	304.8/304.8	[0,90] _{10s}
Compressive Modulus and Strength (0°)	190.5/304.8	[0] ₁₂

The Table-2 shows the mechanical properties measured associated ASTM standards and size of coupons along with stacking sequences. So as to normalize the data and to get accurate consistent results, 7 to 13 coupons were tested from each sample.

Table.2 ASTM Standard, Measured Property, Coupon Dimensions and Stacking Sequence

ASTM Test Method	Measured Property	Coupon Length/ Width (mm)	Stacking Sequence
D3039	Tensile (0°)	254/12.7	[0] ₈
D3039	Tensile (90°)	177.8/25.4	[90] ₁₆
D3518	In-Plane Shear	254/25.4	[+45/-45] _{10s}
D3410	Compressive (0°)	139.7/12.7	[0] ₁₂

The [0, 90]_{10s} laminate was used to cut coupons along the diagonal resulting [+45/-45]_{10s} orientation.

6. Results and Discussions

6.1.1 Tensile Test

ASTM D3039 was employed to determine the tensile strength and modulus. Static loads were introduced into the specimen by hydraulic grips at a standard head displacement rate of 1.27 mm min⁻¹ until the load dropped significantly [11]. The tensile moduli

and strengths were calculated from the slope of stress-strain curves for both 0° and 90° samples.

The Tables 3 and 4 show the average tensile modulus and strength along the fiber direction respectively.

Table.3 Average Tensile Modulus, Standard Deviation and Coefficient of Variation along 0°

Manufacturing Technique	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation
HLU+OOA	140.2	1.82	0.013
HLU+AC	149.5	1.46	0.01
AFP+OOA	158	1.73	0.011
AFP+AC	167.2	2.00	0.011

Table.4 Average Tensile Strength, Standard Deviation and Coefficient of Variation along 0°

Manufacturing Technique	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation
HLU+OOA	1697.2	7.94	0.0046
HLU+AC	1754.6	7.12	0.0040
AFP+OOA	1786.2	7.12	0.0039
AFP+AC	1829	7.51	0.0041

The Tables 5 and 6 show the average tensile modulus and strength perpendicular to the fiber direction respectively.

Table.5 Average Tensile Modulus, Standard Deviation and Coefficient of Variation along 90°

Manufacturing Technique	Tensile Modulus (GPa)	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation
HLU+OOA	8.7	0.6	0.069
HLU+AC	9.8	0.19	0.019
AFP+OOA	10.1	0.3	0.028
AFP+AC	11.2	0.36	0.037

Table.6 Average Tensile Strength, Standard Deviation and Coefficient of Variation along 90°

Manufacturing Technique	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation
HLU+OOA	36.6	3.21	0.087
HLU+AC	43.4	2.30	0.029
AFP+OOA	46.6	2.07	0.044
AFP+AC	48.9	1.81	0.037

6.1.2 In-Plane Shear Test

ASTM D3518 was adopted to examine the In-plane shear modulus and strength. The test was conducted in accordance to the ASTM D3039 tensile test. The coupons instead of having unidirectional fiber had a symmetrical matrix of [+45/-45]₁₀. All the other test conditions were similar to that of D3039 [12]. Tables 6 and 7 show the in-plane shear modulus and strength of the samples respectively.

Table.7 Average In-Plane Shear Modulus, Standard Deviation and Coefficient of Variation of the sample

Manufacturing Technique	Shear Modulus (GPa)	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation
HLU+OOA	4.51	0.13	0.029
HLU+AC	5.05	0.17	0.033
AFP+OOA	5.29	0.13	0.025
AFP+AC	5.76	0.15	0.028

Table.8 Average In-Plane Shear Strength, Standard Deviation and Coefficient of Variation of the sample

Manufacturing Technique	Shear Strength (MPa)	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation
HLU+OOA	72.36	1.52	0.021
HLU+AC	79.08	0.87	0.011
AFP+OOA	81.56	1.02	0.013
AFP+AC	84.84	1.15	0.014

6.1.3 Compressive Test

ASTM D3410 was used to evaluate the compressive strength and modulus. An Illinois Institute of technology Research Institute (IITRI) compression test fixture in accordance with the standard test method was used to provide stability in un-notched compression testing [13]. Static loads were introduced progressively into the specimen via the fixture at a standard head displacement rate of 1.27 mm min⁻¹ until the loads dropped significantly.

Table 9 and 10 show the compressive modulus and strength of the samples.

Table.9 Average Compressive Modulus, Standard Deviation and Coefficient of Variation along 0°

Making Technique	Compressive Modulus (GPa)	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation
HLU+OOA	103.7	1.89	0.018
HLU+AC	114.6	4.03	0.035
AFP+OOA	113.4	5.66	0.05
AFP+AC	125.6	2.80	0.023

Table.10 Average Compressive Strength, Standard Deviation and Coefficient of Variation along 0°

Making Technique	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Standard Deviation	Coefficient of Variation
HLU+OOA	1223.4	6.02	0.0049
HLU+AC	1252.6	6.50	0.0051
AFP+OOA	1248.4	6.91	0.0055
AFP+AC	1276.4	7.7	0.006

6.2 Discussion

In all the tests the samples made by AFP process in combination with pressurized curing out-performed all the other combinations of manufacturing and curing processes. The samples made by AFP and cured without pressure also produced decent and promising results. In almost all the cases these samples produced better results than the samples made by HLU and cured with pressure. However, the

later shows slightly better results in the Compressive Tests.

The Table-11 shows comparative results obtained from all the above tests. It shows each process ranked I, II, III or IV based on the above experimental results, I being the best and IV being the worst.

Table.11 Manufacturing Process Rankings

Manufacturing Technique	Tensile	In-Plane Shear	Compressive
HLU+OOA	IV	IV	IV
HLU+AC	III	III	II
AFP+OOA	II	II	III
AFP+AC	I	I	I

7. Cost-Model Development

The cost savings associated with the OOA prepreg technology is the main driving force for all the advancements we have been seeing in the last few years. To demonstrate this, a comparative cost-model is developed to study the costs associated for a part manufactured by AFP and cured in Autoclave and a part manufactured by AFP but cured OOA.

For developing this cost-model, the following parameters were considered.

- i) A simple part geometry like a cylinder or a flat plate was considered
- ii) The cost of slitted prepreg tape, \$80/lb
- iii) The weight of the prepreg needed, 6 lbs
- iv) Skilled Labor/Technician cost, \$75/hr
- v) AFP Layup rate, 3lb/ hr
- vi) Autoclave/Oven cycle time, 6 hours
- vii) Oven cue time, 3 hours
- viii) Over-head cost of Autoclave, \$180
- ix) Over-head cost of AFP Machine, \$250/hr
- x) Over-head cost of Oven, \$60/hr
- xi) Inspection Costs, \$250/hr
- xii) Inspection time, 1 hour
- xiii) Miscellaneous costs, \$100

The total cost of making a part with AFP and cured OOA, without pressure with the above parameters is \$2,143 compared to \$2,938 for the same part made by AFP but cured in the Autoclave with pressure. There's an increment of 37% in cost; so as to gain 5.8% more Tensile Modulus, 20% more Shear Modulus and 10.8% more Compressive Modulus. In other words, to gain 1 GPa in Tensile Modulus by using the Autoclave curing process a cost of \$86.4 is involved.

In the bar-chart shown below in Figure-12; all the major costs are shown and a comparison is done with respect to the Autoclave and OOA curing cycles.

Fig. 12 Cost comparison for the part manufactured by AFP and cured in Autoclave and OOA

Clearly from the cost model, the cost of Autoclave is one of the major driving factors in determining the cost of manufacturing a composite part. The particular example shown in Figure-12 is for a geometrically simple part, and with increasing size and complexity the cost of Autoclave will go up. Major cost reduction can be obtained on Autoclave Over-heads, Tooling costs, and the costs associated with moving Inventory by taking the Out-of-Autoclave curing path. OOA Technology enables composite manufacturing by eliminating the cost and operation of Autoclave. Perhaps, phenomenal cost

reduction can be obtained from low temperature tooling [14].

8. Conclusion

Conclusions drawn from the work presented in this paper are summarized below:

- i) *Quality*: With the modern advancements in OOA prepreg technology and proper process control over the manufacturing, void free laminates can easily be conceived. The laminate made by AFP and cured without pressure had microscopic structure similar to that of the laminate cured in Autoclave with pressure. Both of them had very limited resin-rich areas.
- ii) *Mechanical Properties*: The samples made by AFP and processed in Autoclave had the best properties, followed closely by the samples made by AFP cured without pressure. The HLU samples were well behind the AFP samples in all the tests.
- iii) *Cost Analysis*: High cost savings can be resulted by avoiding the costs associated with the Autoclave; and with the elimination of Autoclave, further cost reduction in tooling, inventory transportation and operator costs can also be achieved. The economics of curing the samples without Autoclave were promising.

Overall, the automated AFP processing with outperformed HLU processing in every test and analysis; also the samples cured without pressure using AFP produced results comparable to that of the samples cured with pressure that too with substantial cost reductions.

References

- [1] M. Bannister “Challenges for composites into the next millennium - a reinforcement perspective”. Elsevier, Composites: Part A 32, pp 901-910, 2001.
- [2] B. Shirinzadeh, C.W. Foong, G. Alici and G. Cassidy “Fabrication Process of open surfaces by robotic fibre placement”. Elsevier, Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing 20, pp 17-28, 2004.
- [3] M. Brilliant, “Out-of-Autoclave Manufacturing of Complex Shape Composite Laminates”. Master Thesis, McGill University, 2010.
- [4] Umeco Advanced Composites PLC(Cytec Industries), <http://www.umeco.com/News-and-Events/Press-releases/2012/GE-Aviation-calls-on-Umeco>
- [5] Tencate Advanced Composites, “Technical Data Sheet for TC 250 Resin System”, TC250DS_070312, 2012.
- [6] D. Dykeman, “Minimizing uncertainty in cure modeling for composites manufacturing”. Doctoral Thesis, University of British Columbia, 2008.
- [7] B.S. Hayes and L.M. Gammon “Optical Microscopy of Fiber Reinforced Composites”. ASM International, 2010.
- [8] V. M. Drakonakis, J. C. Seferis and C. C. Domanidis, “Curing Pressure Influence of Out-of-Autoclave Processing on Structural Composites for Commercial Aviation”. Advances in Material Science and Engineering, Article ID 356824, 2013.
- [9] C. Dang, E. Carter, G. Butler and K. Bernetich, “Mechanical Comparison of Out-of-Autoclave Prepreg Part to conventional Autoclave Prepreg Part”. American Helicopter Society 67th Annual Forum, 2011.
- [10] X. Cai, “Determination of Process Parameters for the Manufacturing of Thermoplastic Composite Cones using Automated Fiber Placement”, Master Thesis, Concordia University, 2012.
- [11] “ASTM D3039/D3039M-08 Standard test method for tensile properties of polymer matrix composite materials”, ed. West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International, 2008.
- [12] “ASTM D3518/D3518M-94 Standard test method for In-Plane Shear response of polymer matrix composite materials by tensile test of +45/-45 Laminate”, ed. West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International, 2007.
- [13] “ASTM D3410 / D3410M – 03 Standard test method for Compressive properties of polymer matrix composite materials with Unsupported Gage Section by Shear Loading” ed. West Conshohocken, PA: ASTM International, 2008.
- [14] C. Ridgard, “Advances in low temperature curing prepregs for Aerospace Structures”, 4th International SAMPE Symposium, 2000.